

Hello and welcome to the ONLY 5-STAR mobile Cape Town sensual massage service.

House of Tantra Sensual Massage Cape Town is unique in that we only do outcall sensual massage. We understand the needs of busy execs and world travelers to have access to a top-class, professional and discreet mobile sensual massage service. We are a world-class international service with 9 branches in 5 countries around the world.

Why go to the hassle and risk visiting a seedy massage parlor or a private masseuse, when you can be delivered the very best top-class service you are accustomed to, right to your hotel room door?

We provide outcall erotic massage to high-class hotels in the Cape Town city centre, Waterfront and immediate surrounds.

Exceptions can be made for high-end AirBnB and holiday properties.

We have assembled only the most gorgeous goddesses to sensualize your body, entice your mind, elevate your spirit & keep you forever dreaming... Our goddesses all work on a part-time basis - you are therefore assured of the 'girl-next-door' arriving at your hotel. Start with a touch - end with a smile...

Why not immerse yourself in a world full of sensuality, tenderness, relaxation and the pure joy of life. Massages have a long tradition in the history of mankind and are used for a multitude of purposes: to cure, to relax, for meditation and eroticism.

In our sessions we spoil you using every trick in the book, and we can assure you that every massage is tailored individually to each client's needs.

The best adult sensual massage in Cape Town!

We have been working in the massage business for over 15 years. Our many years delivering mind-blowing sensual massage experiences has allowed us to tweak our sessions with just the right combination of elements - from starting with a lovely full body massage, to the sinfully good body2body journey, to uber-arousing lingam and yoni massages, to the right massage oils, to our gorgeous girl-next-door goddesses.

We cater for sensual massage for men and for couples. We do also offer sensual massages for women on request.

Bookings must be made at least 1 HOUR ahead of the required booking time to ensure that we are able to provide you with your chosen goddess and the perfect level of service.

To make a booking simply complete our online booking form on our website at - www.houseoftantra.com

See you soon!

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